

FINLAND

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE

**FINNISH International Scientific Online
Conference:**

**«INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL
SCIENCE»**

A collection of articles by Asian scholars

Issue 7, Part 1

Indexed databases:

aidlix.com

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference – Tampere, Finland «AID», 2025. Issue 7 Part 1.

Languages of publication: English, Russian, German, Italian, Spanish

The collection consists of scientific research of scientists, graduate students and students who took part in the International Scientific online conference «**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE**». Which took place in Tampere, 2025.

Conference proceedings are recommended for scientists and teachers in higher education establishments. They can be used in education, including the process of post - graduate teaching, preparation for obtain bachelors' and masters' degrees. The review of all articles was accomplished by experts, materials are according to authors copyright. The authors are responsible for content, researches results and errors.

© «AID», 2025

© Authors, 2025

SECTION 1. ARTICLES FROM ASIA

1.	FORMING PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY IN AMATEUR ATHLETES THROUGH SPORTS GAMES Janny Cookel	5
2.	DIDACTIC FEATURES OF THE PROCESS OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY AIMING AT SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS BASED ON A GENDER APPROACH Sharifzoda Sardorbek O'razboy tabib ugli	10
3.	WPFDA STILLAR, TRIGGERLAR VA TEMALAR. Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Jurabayev Javohir	14
4.	LINQ SO'ROVLAR YARATISH Yusupov Mirsaid Abdulazizovich , Nurmatova Xushnozabonu To'ychiboy qizi	20
5.	WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF NATIONAL PAYMENT SYSTEMS Hamroyeva Maftuna Axtamovna	27
6.	DIGITAL EVIDENCE IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS Sanny Devy Loursen	31

**DIDACTIC FEATURES OF THE PROCESS OF PREPARING FUTURE
TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY AIMING AT SOCIALIZATION
OF STUDENTS BASED ON A GENDER APPROACH**

Sharifzoda Sardorbek O‘razboy tabib ugli

Acting Rector of Mamun University,

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences(PhD), Associate Professor

E-mail: sharifzoda_sardorbek@mamunedu.uz

Orcid: 0000-0003-4733-8204

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16594458>

Abstract: This article analyzes the didactic features of the process of preparing future teachers for professional activities aimed at socializing students based on a gender approach. The content, purpose and methodological foundations of the approach aimed at ensuring gender equality in the educational process are considered. The author pays attention to issues such as creating a gender-sensitive educational environment, developing didactic competencies of teachers, and adapting educational content to the principles of gender equality.

Keywords: gender approach, didactic features, professional training, socializing students, didactic competence, gender sensitivity.

Introduction.

The components of the socio-cultural competence of a future teacher should be formed on the basis of mutual interaction. The formation of this competence requires the use of the capabilities of the pedagogical discipline. In this process, students are required to be creative, work in collaboration, systematically master national cultural wealth, and have knowledge about gender models, gender roles, and gender identity. To do this, professors and teachers should organize socio-cultural events that embody socio-cultural relations, and students should demonstrate creative activity and responsiveness in such events. Students should master new knowledge and experience at all stages of socio-cultural adaptation and coordinate this knowledge with their existing ones. The results of monitoring and analyzing the acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies of students show that they cannot always coordinate their existing knowledge with the newly acquired knowledge. This creates difficulties for students in their future activities. All professors and teachers should form motivations for self-development in students using effective pedagogical tools, giving priority to their desire to master socio-cultural knowledge. In order for this process to be organized pedagogically in a purposeful way, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of a specific component of socio-cultural professional competence at a certain stage of the educational process.

It is expedient to create pedagogical conditions for the formation of a specific component of integrative competence in future teachers. These include: the formation of

the main component of integrative competence, the creation of methodological support aimed at the formation of pedagogical competence of an integrative nature in students, the development and activation of self-development motives in future teachers in order to acquire socio-cultural competence.

The components of the components of integrative professional competence formed at the initial stages of education are gradually enriched and improved at subsequent stages. In this process, priority is given to the holistic development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers. As a result, all components of socio-cultural competence in students develop in a gradual way. A study of existing experiences, a retrospective analysis of studies on the development of socio-cultural and professional competence in future teachers based on a gender approach, and historical-cultural approaches showed that the use of international and national, historical, cultural experiences, ethno-pedagogical values, national-regional customs and traditions, sources of folk oral creativity and written literature, ethnographic tools, national costumes, visual arts and musical heritage, and examples of folk crafts is of particular importance in preparing students for pedagogical activities related to the socialization of students based on a gender approach.

Below we will focus on the knowledge of socio-cultural competence and the branches of pedagogical disciplines that students master in each academic year. Because the knowledge provided to students within the framework of the educational blocks serves to form integrative competence in them and ensures the development of professional skills in the field of socialization of students. First of all, in order to prepare future teachers for professional activities related to the socialization of students based on a gender approach, it is recommended to include the elective subject “Development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers” in the elective subjects block. For first-year students, the “Introduction to specialization” course should focus on their creative independent development and preparation for socialization, interpersonal cultural relations. At the same time, it is recommended to include in the content of the curricula and educational blocks for each academic year educational topics and educational materials that serve to form socio-cultural competence in students. In particular, it is necessary to enrich the content of such academic subjects as “Pedagogical skills”, “Theory and history of pedagogy”, “Methodology of teaching education”, “Pedagogical deontology and competence” with such materials. It is also necessary to consider enriching the content of all educational courses included in the category of pedagogical academic subjects with didactic materials and pedagogical approaches aimed at forming socio-cultural competence in future teachers.

In order to form professional competence of a socio-cultural nature in future teachers, it is necessary to consider a wide range of involvement in classroom and extracurricular activities. Because this competence is mainly formed effectively in the process of cultural-

educational, socio-economic, legal, professional, scientific knowledge tools and self-management activities. To do this, it is necessary to clearly define the components of this competence that students need to form in each academic year, the pedagogical goals intended for its formation, forms and methods of classroom and extracurricular work. In particular, it is recommended to provide third-year students with the following:

1. Knowledge, skills, qualifications that ensure socio-moral upbringing, which is a specific component of the formation of socio-cultural competence.

2. The pedagogical goal of forming socio-cultural competence in students is to cultivate such qualities as fairness, conscientiousness, orderliness, honesty, goal-orientedness, determination, self-confidence, organization, demandingness, positive outlook, active citizenship, and the formation of a culture of pedagogical ethics and intellectual labor.

3. Forms and methods of the process of acquiring pedagogical skills aimed at socializing students are presented to students. Knowledge and skills in this area are provided to students through the content of courses in philosophy, cultural studies, general professional disciplines and special fields of study, the foundations of the theoretical activity of a future teacher, and professional ethics.

4. In preparing future teachers for professional activities related to the socialization of students based on a gender approach, cultural and educational events are also of particular importance in addition to the classroom, in which certain components of socio-cultural and professional competence are formed. These include: preparing students for creative work, implementing social actions that reflect the spiritual and moral foundations of interpersonal relationships, organizing “Creative Youth” clubs taking into account the areas of interest of students, preparing discussion situations in student groups, conducting pedagogical trainings of a professional aesthetic nature, organizing dialogue situations that promote the ethics of pedagogical behavior, holding video clips, press conferences and debate situations on the topics of patriotism and tolerance, creative evenings, competitions, contests, participation in student scientific conferences, etc.

Analysis of existing experiences shows that methods, forms, and practical actions aimed at gradually forming socio-cultural competencies in future teachers in order to prepare them for socialization based on a gender approach ensure the effectiveness of the educational process and expand its socio-pedagogical potential. These pedagogical measures accelerate the pedagogical process and allow for the systematic implementation of goal-oriented pedagogical actions within each subject.

REFERENCES:

1. Абдраимов, А.А. Гендерная педагогика: учебное пособие / А.А. Абдраимов. — Ташкент: Учкун, 2016. — 156 с.

2. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). Strategies for preparing future teachers for pedagogical activity on the basis of a gender approach. *International bulletin of engineering and technology*, 3(4), 173-176.
3. Sardorbek, O., Sharifzoda, L., & Karimov, H. Q. (2022). Gender yondashuv asosida o'quvchi-qizlarda ijtimoiymadaniy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish omillari. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(7), 371-375.
4. Sharifzoda, S. O. Strategies for forming competencies in students based on an integrative approach. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies/ISSN*, 2750-8587.
5. [Factors for preparing students for pedagogical activities aimed at socialization on the basis of a gender approach](#), S.Sharifzoda - ... Conference on Management, Economics & Social ..., 2023.
6. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). Oliy pedagogik ta'limda gender yondashuvini amalga oshirishning ijtimoiy zarurati. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 9), 263-268.
7. Sharifzoda, S. (2024). Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning gender yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarni ijtimoiylashtirishga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik tayyorgarligining ahamiyati. *Tamaddun nuri jurnali*, 9(60).
8. Саидова, М.Ж. Гендерный подход в образовании / М.Ж. Саидова. — Ташкент: Фан, 2020. — 128 с.